

**LANDFILL AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOLID WASTE DISPOSAL SYSTEM
IN YOLA AND ITS ENVIRONS, North East Of Nigeria**

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ABSTRACT

The current solid waste disposal system in Yola and its environs has been out dated and outgrown by the population of Inhabitants All sorts of solid waste, including medical wastes are disposed in an open dump in an irregular manner. The topographical and geological condition of the area is favourable for sanitary landfill. It is located at the topographically level land of the Upper Benue River Basin and the site (s) is underlain by the Bima sandstone which constitutes natural hydraulic barriers, consisting sandstone, mud and clay layers. The terrestrial Bima sandstone formation has a permeability of 10^{-3} to 10^{-5} cm/sec.

In addition, a lot of deposit of montmorillonitic clay layer is found at nearby town of Numan which is underlain by the Numanha shale formation.. The area has an abundant clay layer deposition which is going to be used as liners. It has a permeability of 10^{-7} to 10^{-8} cm/sec. This material will thus be supplemented with synthetic membrane which will serve as liners for effective protection of the underground water. Also recommended are baseliners, final cover, toe embankment and drainage of leachate and gas vent.

KEYWORDS:-Solid waste, disposal system, landfill, Yola and its environs.

1.0 BACKGROUND INTRODUCTION.

The disposal of solid waste is defined as placement of the waste so that it will no longer impact the society (Oraegbune, 2000). The disposal of refuse generated by urban center is an acute problem throughout the world and is not specific or peculiar to Yola and its environs alone. The purpose is merely to get ride of the waste materials of an individuals or a society's sight with the least possible cost and effort (NATPS , 1998).

However, there is reluctance on the part of the people(s) to spend time and money on materials.

As a result of this attitude, there is a constant struggle to separate men's waste materials from his environment. The problem is further compounded because of changes in living habit and the nature of the materials constituting the wastes. Due to improved living standards and increased production, refuse has been increasing in volume per capita and changing in physical characteristics for the last several decades (NAPTS, 1998). Currently, a solid waste disposal site in the study area is being surrounded by the growing population and inadequate alternative disposal system. The open dump system used has become inadequate with the uncontrolled

disposal sites over the town. All varieties of solid wastes, including medical wastes are stored at the present sites and at irregular manner. There are also unclear refuse all over the streets of Yola and its environs, which continue to cause public nuisance through blockage of roads, drainage and open spaces. The monthly and bi-monthly general cleaning exercises have not helped matters. The problems therefore have serious health implications and affect the aesthetic value of our environment (Oraegbune, 2000).

A comprehensive study which would delineate the magnitude of this problem would be beneficial to the government in its future environmental policy. The problems of the environment have resulted in many researches which include finding out the impact of the disposal of solid wastes from immediate environment. Many studies on this aspect of the environment have been carried out. Despite the efforts of the Adamawa State Environmental protection Agency (ASEPA), Adamawa State Urban Planning and Development Authority (ASUPDA), Infrastructural Development Fund (IDF) and some members of the public in evaluating the waste generated, still heaps of waste are found along the streets of Yola and its environs (Gundiri, 1995). To ensure environmental quality, the agencies constructed incinerators at strategic places and pay loaders were employed to remove wastes such as polythene bags or other materials, and papers are burnt in the incinerators directly while ashes were finally transported to final disposal areas. Due to rapid increase in the volume of waste generated, the above system faded away and was replaced by the placing of DAF containers in all over the town (i.e. at strategic positions as recommended by the World Bank Assisted Programme (DarAl-Handasah, 1986).

As rightly observed by (DarAl-Handasah, 1986) that Yola and its environs had been neglected city in Nigeria. It is therefore long over due for standard disposal system. There have been tremendous increases in volume and ranges of solid wastes. This is because of the rapid increase in population which gives rise to high intensification of various activities in the various sectors within the area (i.e. commercial, residential and industrial sectors), resulting in indiscriminate dumping of solid waste by the populace (DarAl-Handasah, 1986).

For a very long period now, open dump system has been used mostly in Yola and its environs as well as any available open space. The environmental protection agency and infrastructural Development fund which are the agencies responsible for evacuating solid waste have their sites (open dump) or collecting canter (78 numbers) scattered within Figs.1&2) Yola area. Despite these, there is no standard disposal system designed or provided to dispose the waste. For instance between 1996 to 1999, the total volume of wastes generated and disposed after the scavengers was $118,737\text{m}^3$ (ASEPA, 1999)

Refuse disposal is carried out at tips outside the towns. Borrow pits excavated in connection with road construction are used.

The tips serving Jimeta are located along the Numan and Mubi roads, 14 km and 8km away from the town respectively. The Yola tip is located along the towns southern by pass road (Figs.1&2). The tips do not affect any water course and there is no evidence of water pollution (Oraegbune, 2000)

In view of the present characteristic of refuse in the urban areas under study, the incineration method would not be suitable due to low combustible content in the refuse (Table 1). In addition, compost method is not suitable due to the high cost of biostabilizers process. Even if a suitable price is expected for reuse of compost in nearby agricultural land, any recouped cost by selling compost can only materializes after adequate marketing structure of this item is well established. It will also take some time before marketing of such compost.

On this basis, Land fill method of disposal of refuse should be chosen or considered against the present system of open dumping because enough area of land is available for future development.

1.2 THE STUDY AREA:-Yola, the capital city of Adamawa State was established in 1841 by Modibo Adama, the flag bearer of the nineteenth century Islamic Revivalist . Yola has served as the capital of the Emirate of Fombina (1841-1902), Adamawa province (1902-1960), Gongola State (1976-1991) and currently Adamawa State (1991-date). It is located on latitude 09.14^{0c} and longitude 12.8^{0c} E, The city has tropical climate, marked by rainy and dry seasons. The maximum temperature recorded for Yola is 39.7^{0c} (Futy student Hand book, 1995-2000) and has a population of 3,178,950 National Population Commission (NPC, 2005)

1.3 STRATIGRAPHY AND HYDROGEOLOGY OF THE SITES.

The study area is underlain by continental Bima sandstone which is composed predominantly of fine to medium grained sand stone with interculations of shales and clays. The sand stone ranges from weakly consolidated to highly indurated form but the latter appears to predominate. Surface exposures of Bima sandstone found around Girei, Yola and Kwanan Wire/ Sangere areas as well as Yola-Mubi way, Tollgate, Vinikilang has a distinct lithology consisting of fine to coarse grained pebbly sand stone with intercalation of clays shale and mud stone (Oraegbune, 2000). It shows a great variation in thickness ranging from 15m to more than 20m. The hydroliithologic analyses of borehole logs revealed the presence of three aquifer systems namely the upper unfinned and the lower sem-confined aquifer systems (Okirigwe,1995). The Upper unconfined system consist of fine to medium grained sand stone which has direct hydraulic connection with land fill locations in the areas. The thickness of the aquifer varies from 30m at the Federal Poiytechnic, Yola Campus to 60m at Girei with an average value of about 45m (Oraegbune,2000) The depth to static water level varies from about 2m at Federal Polytechnic, Yola Campus to 48m at Girei (Okirigwe,1995). Both the clay stones and clays which serve as semi-confined to confined layer indicate a hydraulic conductivity range of 10⁻³ to 10⁻⁵ cm /sec where as the upper unconfined aquifer system has a hydraulic conductivity range 10⁻¹ to 10⁻² cm/sec (Okirigwe, 1995).

In addition, the general ground water flow direction to the North East, is from North West to South West where as to the North West it flows from North West to south East (ground water Figs.3)

1.2 AIMS AND OBJECTIVES: - The aims of this study is to

- (i) Identify the problems associated with refuse disposal and how to solve it.

TABLE 1 SOLID WASTE COMPOSITION IN THE STUDY AREA

S/NO.	Composition	Average(kg)	Percentage(%)
1	Fruit and Vegetables	2.9	1.12
2	Leaves and grasses	46.82	18.02
3	Wood/saw dust	1.02	0.39
4	Food wastes	20.23	7.78
5	Paper/card board	6.51	2.50
6	Textile	11.70	4.50
7	Glasses	1.36	0.52
8	Bones/heaps/horns	1.88	0.72
9	Ferrous metal/tins/oans	6.91	2.66
10	Plastic/rubber	2.00	0.77
11	Ashes	44.43	17.09
12	Demolition/construction wastes	2.84	1.09
13	Polyethene bags	22.67	8.72
14	leather	0.004	1.5x10-3
15	hurk	72.07	27.72
16	Animal dung	15.52	5.97
17	Special waste	1.48	0.57
18	Density	260 kg/m ³	100%

(ii) To design and develop an engineering alternative of solid waste in the areas.

2 **METHODOLOGY AND DATA MATERIALS REQUIRED.** The data required for the purpose of this study is data on solid waste disposal. This data include the following

- (i) Composition of solid wastes
- (ii) Solid waste generation
- (iii) Geologic factor/underlying soil strata.
- (iv) Hydrology
- (v) Designing data
- (vi) Topographic map.

2.1 SOURCES OF DATA COLLECTION:

Basically three types of data sources were used for this research work.

Basically three types of data sources were used for this research work.

- (i) Data from sample collection of solid wastes from various homes, commercials and industrial/ institutions,
- (ii) Data from Adamawa State water environmental and sanitation agency (WESA).
- (iii) Adamawa State Environmental Protection Agency (ASEP)
- (iv) Adamawa State Urban Planning and Development Authority (ASUPDA)
- (v) Data from newspapers, magazines, seminar paper/workshops, test Books, Journals etc.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

SANITARY LANDFILL DESIGN TRENCH/CELL TYPE.

The following are the condition favorable for developing sanitary land fill (trench/cell type)

- (i) The existence of sand stone formation of between 10^{-5} to 10^{-3} cm/sec of hydraulic conductivity (Okirigwe,1995)which can be supplemented by the abundant formation of highly impermeable montmorillonite clay of 10^{-8} to 10^{-7} cm/sec of hydraulic conductivity from near by town of (Numan and Demsa), (Oraegbune.,2000). This lightly impermeable clay will be transported to site at lower cost to act as liners (Oraegbune, 2000). It occurs at a distance of about 45km or less than 35minutes drive (haulage distance) from Yola.
- (ii) There is an absence of ground water within the depth of 2m of the landfill
- (iii) Suitable topographic condition (physiographic Fig.4 and cross-section of Yola and its environs).

In addition to the factors listed above, soil material required for daily Weekly covering needs is abundant in the area. In fact, the entire area has abundant land mass which can be used for years

Other criteria to be considered for site selection to design trench sanitary landfill is the distance from features such as lakes, river's flood plains, marsh, Natural Park, reservation area, airport, and major high ways. This criterion is met by almost all the areas proposed for the landfill.

The engineering criteria for the proposed trench sanitary landfill includes

- (a) Base liners
- (b) Toe embankment or bond
- (c) Final cover
- (d) Leachate collection /control system
- (e) Gas gravel vent or gas extraction well depending *on the quantity and usage*
- (f) *Surface* water drainage
- (g) Natural soil attenuation

The proposed trench landfills will be located in three places namely

Kwanan wire /sangere along Numan road near B.H.No AD/TH 10/006/95 North- West of J/Yoia, Girei- 1 near B.H. No.18, North - East of J/Yoia, and mbanba-1 near B.H No. 15 (South- East of Yoia along Fufore road. They are underlain by natural barriers and are planned to be covered by artificial 1:3 or 3 to 6%, which is common for most land fills. Also provided at the cover surface are trees and shrubs to prevent recipitation from penetrating to the land fill.

Figures (5a,b& c) indicate the protective soil cover, filter medium, solid waste leachate collection system and liners, toe embankment base liner and final cover as well as schematic cross-section of secured landfill.

It has for some times been recommended and is now becoming practice to place waste in cells within the landfill site which allows small controlled disposal operation and minimizes leachate protection. It also permits segregation of clean and polluted water on the site and early capping aid restoration of the tipped cell area.

Cell construction therefore forms part of the engineering works before tipping and an assessment should be made at this stage to determine the volume of materials required for cell construction, daily cover and final capping top soil. Each days waste should form one cell. The daily design cell is 6m x 6m x 2m for the day's waste disposal with a cover at each end of day work of 150mm of earth or suitable material. The slope of working face of formation is 2:1 or 3:1 or alternatively 0.5 to 1% while the side slope is 2:1

Finally the total volume of the proposed land filled is about 1301870m³ or approximately about 2310,000 m³ while each of the three sites has a volume of about 772840 m³ or approximately about 773,000m³. The ratio of waste and the total cover is 5:1, with regard to

volume. Each site covers an area of 386420m² or 387000m² while 40% additional area is provided for feature landfill development or expansion.

The projected volume of solid waste for the next 6 years in 2,310,000m³ or about 600000 tons (2003 to 2009).

3.1 GENERAL SPECIFICATION.

- (a) Access road (paved all weather access road)
- (b) Temporary road to unloading area.
- (c) Landfill area is 540, 000m²
- (d) Working area is 38700m² for each site.
- (e) Reserved area is 155000m² for each.
- (f) Length is 1390m
- (g) Dept is 2m
- (h) Width is 278m
- (i) Landfill (trench /cell type)
- (j) Formation slope is 3:1, final cover slope, 3% to 6%, side slope 2:1
- (k) Surface drainage: Use 25cm& perforated pipe partially buried in the slope of 6% gradient or alternatively install drainage ditches to divert surface water runoff.
- (l) Intermediate cover material: - maximize of on site soil materials.
- (m) Waste cover ratio is about 5 to 1 or 10 to 1.
- (n) Clay liners (montmonillonte 10⁻⁷ to 10⁻⁸ of 0.6m to 1m
- (o) Synthetic membrane thermoplastic elastomers or high density polyethylene
- (p) Leachate collection system.
- (q) Ground water diversion
- (r) Use gas gravel vent to stop gas migration
- (s) Toe embankment construction should be between 1-1.5m high at slope of 1:2

The investigation which was focused on the soil, waste composition hydraulic conductivity and topographic conditions, and other location criteria show that sanitary landfill method (trench/cell) is the best alternative disposal method "for now" in Yola and its environs.

The study area falls within the Upper Benue Basin which is about 203000000km² in expanse (Okirigwe, 1995). The topography is generally flat and typically fluvial. It is underlain by Bima Sandstone. The Bima Sandstone constitute potentially good aquifers and covers about two – thirds (2/3) of the area. It consists of fine to coarse grained sandstone, with intercalations of whitish and red siltstone, mudstones and clays. The alluvial deposit consisting of silts and silt sands is largely confined along the banks of River Benue whereas west of the study areas around Numan and Demsa are underlain by thick shale and clays of the Numanha shale formation. The clays of the Numanha shale which is believed to be montmorillonites indicate hydraulic conductivity values ranging from 10⁻⁸ cm/sec to 10⁻⁷ cm/sec is clearly a suitable material for use in landfill construction.

Thus, with clays as a material for lining, the alluvium that fills the bottom of the topographic area would constitute both the construction as well as interlayer materials. Research has shown that the study area has relatively moderate rainfall and considerable ground water reserve which resulted in gave rise to numerous boreholes for tapping water from the reserve (Okirigwe, 1995). Thus, with the existence of abundant clay deposits in neighboring Numan and Demsa areas, it is convenient that the landfill method constructed with synthetic membrane to eliminate ground water flukes would be a viable disposal method in Yola and its environs.

Also important to note is that the construction of a sanitary landfill and use of modern disposal techniques will minimize environmental pollution. For example Lagos which has been using sanitary landfill disposal system for years, haven't reported underground water pollution or explosion from methane gas (LSEPMA, 2000)

Therefore, it is recommended that landfill system will help in eliminating the indiscriminate open dumping of solid wastes which is currently being practiced in Yola and its environs, and will consequently result in and pollution free environment

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